

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

The Education and Methodological Complex "Im Klartext A2": Continuity and Innovation

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Abstract

In the field of professional education, the problem of creating innovative teaching aids and educational and methodological complexes is currently especially acute. The tasks and functions of teaching materials in a foreign language are fundamentally changing and becoming more complicated in connection with the changing requirements of the labour market for young specialists, the duration of study at universities and the increasing informatization and digitalization of processes. It is necessary to critically rethink the experience accumulated in the field of compiling textbooks and education-methodical complexes in foreign languages and optimize their content and structure, taking into account new requirements. The article undertakes a comparative analysis of the classic textbook and the education-methodical complex of the new generation in the German language. The manuals are analyzed from the point of view of the content, the authenticity of the proposed materials and the communicative component of the exercises and tasks. The genres of the texts used and the types of tasks for the extraction of information while reading are highlighted. The results of the analysis showed that the teaching materials of a new type include the most effective traditional types of exercises and tasks, at the same time, the compilers make an attempt to use language and speech exercises comprehensively, lexical and grammar material is worked out in interaction, and the system of exercises is aimed at the formation and improvement of communicative, sociocultural, strategic and pragmatic competencies. The structure of the teaching materials of a new type also includes a program of study in a multimedia class for the development of pronunciation skills using authentic samples of speech and listening skills with full or partial extraction of information from texts of different genres, selected taking into account the level of students and the subject matter of the main parts of the teaching materials. .

Keywords: German; authentic textbooks; exercises; tasks; multimedia component.

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Introduction

The processes of social and economic changes and the rapid development of new technologies have a direct impact on society as a whole and all its spheres, in particular professional education. Students of higher education institutions, especially those studying in areas related to international relations, are aware of the importance and necessity of learning a foreign language. The intensification of international cooperation in the context of globalization also motivates students, since the knowledge of foreign languages improves the prospects for professional growth.

The transition to a new paradigm of education and the increasing competition in the field of education services require higher education institutions to radically change the training of specialists competent in general professional, in communicative, speech and foreign language relations. Requirements for intellectual and moral potential, as well as for the general culture of a person and abilities that allow them to adequately express themselves in situations of intercultural communication, are growing rapidly (Plekhanova, 2007). Besides, information support plays an increasingly important role in the effective organization of the education process at the university.

All this complicates the tasks which the teacher of a foreign language faces since with a decrease in the share of classroom hours in the study load and the duration of study in connection with the transition to a multi-stage system of higher education, the requirements for the formation of foreign language communicative competence, including linguistic, sociocultural, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, discursive and strategic subcompetencies (Zimina, 2018).

At the turn of the century, these factors led to the need to create new textbooks on a foreign language in higher schools, since there were no authentic manuals that could meet the above requirements (Kravtsova & Yastrebova, 2019). Education and methodological complexes (EMC) created in the countries of the target language are becoming popular. One of the main advantages of EMC data is their authenticity. However, one should not lose sight of the fact that foreign education and methodological complexes were developed without focusing on the national specifics of students and teachers (Majala, 2019), moreover, these manuals are far from the requirements of the modern education system in Russia and do not correspond to the realities of domestic professional and business reality. (Tareva & Tarev, 2014). It is also noted that in some cases, authenticity can become an obstacle to the formation of intercultural competence (Riedner, 2018).

Universities, departments and teachers are faced with the problem of choosing a high-quality textbook. In recent decades, there has been a tendency to create domestic teaching aids and educational and methodological complexes for a particular university and faculty. On the one hand, this made it possible to fill the vacuum in the absence of modern teaching aids, on the other hand, there is a large flow of teaching materials, which often copy texts and assignments from foreign textbooks, adapting them to the requirements of the Russian education system. At the same time, in the domestic theory and practice of teaching foreign languages, a lot of developments, methods and tools have been accumulated that have proven their effectiveness, and thoughtless rejection of traditions and established practices can lead to a deterioration in the results of the learning process. It seems relevant to conduct a comprehensive study of the problem of continuity and innovation in teaching aids of the new generation to identify traditional and new structural components, forms of work, types of exercises and tasks.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are to analyze the structure and content of the teaching materials of the new generation "Im Klartext A2" and the classic textbook of the German language Zavyalova V.M. and Ilyina L.V. "Practical course of the German language" (2003), classification of text material and assignments, identification of traditional and innovative components in the content and structure of the teaching materials "Im Klartext A2".

Literature review

The classification of exercises and tasks in textbooks in foreign languages has repeatedly become the goal of the study. E.I. Passov (2002) identifies the following types of exercises: preparatory (lexical and grammar exercises that allow you to accumulate the necessary vocabulary), communicative (based on imitation of speech communication) and creative (natural communication, information exchange). It is noted that the most difficult are creative exercises because they imply a situation that is close to real life.

I.L. Bim (1997) assigns a primary role to the development of elementary communicative competence in its basic components: linguistic, thematic, socio-cultural and compensatory. In EMC I.L. Bim and N.D. Galskova traditional exercises are used when teaching vocabulary, for example, substitution, word composition, search for antonyms, ordering, elimination of an extra word. As grammar exercises, exercises are offered for filling out tables, substitution, transformation, combining lexical and grammar material and exercises for performing according to a sample, for completing sentences. Conditional speech exercises are aimed at improving skills and are focused more on the form, and not on the function of the language.

The modern learning process in foreign language education in higher education involves the introduction and active use of innovative forms. At the same time, the applied innovations, for example, the competence-based approach, the modular principle, as well as the widespread use of information and communication technologies in no way cancel the previous methods, but rather complement them, which makes it possible to form basic knowledge and a set of skills and abilities (Rainer E . Wicke, 2017). The task of automating skills, the so-called drill, does not lose its relevance when setting pronunciation and intonation, mastering grammar structures and memorizing lexical units (Bullweg, Drum, Hufeisen, Klippel & Pilypaityte, 2019). At the same time, it is noted that such exercises are not the end of a modern foreign language lesson, they are intermediate steps towards the realization of communicative goals, to the exchange of information with other people (Funk, Kuhn, Skiba, Spaniel-Weise & Wicke, 2017).

It should be borne in mind that modern textbooks should be aimed at developing students' readiness for international communication, developing the competencies necessary in intercultural interaction, which will help to form effective communication strategies in a foreign language environment (Plekhanova, 2007; Safonova, 2019).

Rösler and Würffel (2020) summarize the requirements for a modern foreign language textbook. Such a textbook should provide a lexical minimum and regional geographic information within a certain topic, introduce grammar structures and demonstrate their functions, offer material for training and consolidating linguistic phenomena, train in interaction the skills of speaking and writing, reading and listening, create situations for communication using different social forms, contain texts of different genres. The authors note the complication of the structure of the modern methodological complex and distinguish as mandatory components a textbook, workbook, audio texts and video clips in various media and, as additional, bilingual glossaries, online exercises, applications, files for interactive whiteboards.

Methodology

For the study, the method of meaningful, structural and comparative analysis, the classification method, the corpus analysis method, and the method of registration and ranking of numerical data were used.

The objects of the research were the "Practical course of the German language" and the education-methodical complex "Im Klartext A2". As for "Practical course of the German language" Zavyalova V.M. with additions and changes, we can state that it has been republished since 1963 and is a classic textbook with which several generations of German philologists have mastered the German language. The first editions were developed within the framework of the grammar-translation method of teaching a foreign language, with an emphasis on teaching reading and translation; later, during reprints, conditional communicative tasks were included in the textbook, nevertheless, the textbook is still an example of a traditional German textbook. EMC "Im Klartext A2" was developed within the framework of the communicative-activity and competence-based approach to teaching foreign languages and aims to form students' competencies in five types of speech activity: reading, listening, speaking, writing, language mediation (interpretation and translation).

Within the framework of the research, the structure and content of textbooks, as well as workbooks and curriculum in the multimedia classroom of the teaching materials "Im Klartext A2" were analyzed. Textbook texts were classified according to a genre and temporal relevance. The tasks of the textbook, workbook and multimedia class program are divided into exercises aimed at developing lexical-grammar, pronunciation and auditory skills, and tasks that form the competence of speaking and writing, translation, extracting information from heard and read texts, as well as watch videos ... The types of exercises that were traditionally used in the Soviet and Russian methods of teaching foreign languages within the framework of grammar-translation and communicative methods, on the one hand, and new types of exercises and tasks characteristic of the latest generation of teaching materials, created in line with the communicative-activity-based and competence-based approaches, are determined.

Results

The "Practical German Course" (2003) consists of an introductory phonetic course with 10 lessons and 24 lessons of the main course. The methodological recommendations do not reflect information on what level of German language proficiency within the framework of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages this textbook corresponds. The lessons of the main course are characterized by a general structure, including an explanation of grammar material (in Russian), education inauthentic texts of a monologue and dialogical nature, explanations for the lexical units of the lesson, a block of exercises on the vocabulary of the text and grammar of the lesson, a large number of translation exercises, as well as a section "Business vocabulary" and, starting with lesson V, adapted literary texts. There are no authentic texts of other genres in the textbook. Most education texts are neutral in terms of relevance, at the same time, there are outdated words and forms of address: Kassettenrekorder, Schreibmaschine, Wählscheibe, Gestatten Sie, etc. The tasks for the following types of texts are used: answering questions, determining correct and incorrect statements, text translation into Russian, retelling of the text.

EMC "Im Klartext" consists of two parts corresponding to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages A1 and A2, having a common structure and consisting of a textbook, a workbook, a curriculum in a multimedia classroom and a course for the development of auditory and speech skills and competencies on an electronic learning platform ed.mgimo.

The chapters of the textbook have a unified structure and include phonetic exercises in each chapter due to the lack of an introductory phonetic course, authentic education texts adapted taking into account the A2 level, with an active vocabulary and exercises for the formation of reading competencies, an explanation of grammar material (in Russian) and grammar exercises compiled using an active vocabulary and lexical units within the lesson topic, tasks for the formation of oral and written speech, translation tasks and a glossary of words for the lesson with grammar characteristics of lexical units, translation into Russian and an example of use.

A striking distinctive feature of the design of the teaching materials "Im Klartext A2" is the abundance of illustrative material, while in the "Practical course of the German language" there are no illustrations. Images serve as a good help for more effective assimilation of lexical units with a specific meaning, enhance the emotional component concerning the material being learned, and serve as a starting point for statements and discussions (Gehring, 2018).

The workbook, like the textbook, is divided into chapters and contains lexical and grammar exercises and translation tasks for the formation of linguistic competence, additional reading texts with tasks to check reading comprehension, practice tests with a self-assessment scale. All exercises in the workbook are provided with keys, except for translation exercises due to the variability of correct answers.

The texts of the textbook and workbook can be divided into different groups depending on the genre, content relevance and competencies formed. The distribution of textbook texts by genre is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Distribution of texts of the textbook "Im Klartext A2" by genre

The workbook additionally presents such types of text as formal and informal emails, statistics,

advertisements, anecdotes, poems, fairy tales and legends. Obviously, in their future professional activities, beginners will deal primarily with informational texts, this is due to the predominance of this genre in the content structure of the textbook. At the same time, the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages provides for the formation of skills in extracting information from texts of other genres, which are also presented in the textbook and workbook.

To identify the meaningful relevance of the texts, their lexical composition was analyzed, neologisms were identified and an analysis of their word usage in the corpus of modern German was carried out. Of the 39 texts of the textbook, 18 texts use words denoting realities, developments, discoveries, inventions and social phenomena that have become widespread since 2000. For example, words like Navi, Handy-Akku, Cosplay-Event, Modeberater, Sneaker, Kaufsucht, Pop-Up-Fenster, Blog, Nesthocker, Online-Flirt, Digitalisierung, Wiki, Online-Banking, WhatsApp-Nachricht, Twitter, Brexit et al can be found in the Corpus of Modern German from 2000 onwards. Thus, the textbook texts reflect the current state of society and allow you to simulate real communication situations. At the same time, some of the texts have a timeless relevance, for example, biographies of famous people, narrative texts, information from a guidebook about attractions.

Depending on the purpose of teaching, the texts of the textbook and workbook can be divided into the following types: education texts for the presentation of a certain grammar structure (for example, a student's story of how he spent the winter holidays in the past tense perfect), texts for search reading, texts for introductory reading, etc. Learning Reading Texts with Full Information Extraction. Depending on the purpose of training and the genre of the text, the wording of the tasks varies. In addition to traditional answers to questions and definitions of correct and incorrect statements, there are tasks such as:

- Match parts of the sentences.
- Match image and text.
- Which of the characters in the text expressed these opinions?
- Find the correct sequence of parts of the text.
- Determine in which of the gaps in the text the following sentences can be inserted.
- Answer the questions of the psychological test and determine your type.
- Advise Sandra et al.

Thus, in the "Practical Course of the German Language" and the textbook "Im Klartext A2", one can distinguish similar structural components (explanation of grammar material, lexical and grammar exercises, translation exercises), however, a clearer structural division of the EMC into a textbook, a workbook should be noted and a program for working in a multimedia class, as well as greater content and a genre variety of texts in the teaching materials of the new generation and their differentiation according to the purpose of teaching and tasks.

Let us consider grammar and vocabulary exercises in the "Practical Course of the German Language". The following types of grammar exercises are used: oral conjugation of verbs in different tense forms, filling in gaps with endings, pronouns, verb forms, articles; formulation of questions for proposals; changing the purpose of the statement of the sentence (transformation from interrogative motivating, from declarative to interrogative); changing affirmative statements to negative ones; answers to questions and responses to incentive exercises; a combination of two simple sentences into a compound one. In lexical exercises, it is required to insert words that are suitable in meaning, replace the selected words with antonyms or synonyms. As a rule, we are talking about isolated sentences, grammar structures are not necessarily trained on the vocabulary of the current lesson. Translation exercises are very diverse. Students translate all German texts and dialogues of the lesson into Russian, isolated sentences and dialogues from German into Russian and from Russian into German, answer questions in German using these Russian phrases, translate phrases from Russian into German and compose with them offers. The advantage of this approach is early

training in translation as a type of speech activity (Bi, 2020).

In the EMC "Im Klartext A2" all grammar exercises of the textbook and workbook are built on lexical units corresponding to the topic of the chapter and are aimed at the complex formation of lexical and grammar skills, which facilitates their transfer into oral and written speech (Fandrych & Thurmair, 2018). In addition to the traditional grammar exercises found in the Practical German Course, the following types of tasks are used to form speech skills and contribute to the development of communicative competence:

- Fill in the blanks in the questions and ask these questions to the interlocutor.
- Use these phrases in questions to the interlocutor.
- Complete the sentences.
- Formulate tips.
- Describe one of the images. The interlocutor guesses the image number.
- What adjectives / verbs are combined with these nouns? Find matches and make sentences.
- How has... changed? Write in adjectives-antonyms with correct endings.
- Agree or object. Use addition clauses.
- Determine the correct sequence of actions and formulate the instruction (in the passive voice / imperative mood).

In the education complex "Im Klartext A2" the task type "information gaps" (Carola Surkamp, 2017) is widely used to automate grammar structures: Ask your partner for the missing information. This type of assignment, presented in Figure 2, is widely used in textbooks of foreign publishing houses but has not yet entered German textbooks by Russian authors.

Fig. 2.

6. WECHSELSPIEL. Büroalltag von Markus und Antje.

Was macht er / sie, wenn...?

Muster: A. Was macht Markus, wenn er Hunger hat?

B. Wenn Markus Hunger hat, geht er in die Kantine.

A.

Was macht ... , wenn ...?	Markus	Antje
Hunger haben	?	eine Banane essen
Hilfe brauchen	den Kollegen fragen	?
früh aufstehen müssen	?	früh ins Bett gehen

B.

Was macht ... , wenn ...?	Markus	Antje
Hunger haben	in die Kantine gehen	?
Hilfe brauchen	?	die Chefin fragen
früh aufstehen müssen	den Wecker auf 5:00 Uhr stellen	?
Stress im Büro haben	?	die beste Freundin anrufen

Translation tasks were also included in the "Im Klartext A2" EMC, but the authors moved away from

lexical and grammar translation as one of the means of forming linguistic competence and tried to formulate communication tasks for translation exercises and tasks. The translation of isolated sentences was partially preserved in the exercises of the workbook as a means of controlling the assimilation of grammar and vocabulary of the lesson. These translations are performed by students in writing and checked by the teacher. The textbook uses three types of translation exercises:

- written translation from Russian into German of texts of various genres: lists, catalogs, information brochures, menus, advertising texts, personal and official emails, biographies, interviews, etc.;
- interpretation into German from a sheet of coherent monologue text on the topic of the lesson, while working a partner checks the correctness of the translation using the German version of the same text placed in a parallel column (Im Tandem);
- oral two-way translation from hearing, during which two students portray a Russian and a German, and the third translates their dialogue (Dolmetscherspiele).

The following types of assignments are offered in the "Practical Course of the German Language" for the formation of the competences of speaking and writing:

- Dialogue speech: Translate the dialogue into German and act it out. / Create a sample of microdialogues. / Talk about "...".
- Monologue speech: Answer the questions. / Retell the text. / Tell us about ... (your apartment, your studies, your city, etc.).

The tasks "Talk about ..." and "Tell about ..." in the "Practical course of the German language" are already communicative, since they imply the expression of one's own opinion and the transfer of information about oneself. Similar types of tasks are also used in the teaching and learning method "Im Klartext A2", the rest of the tasks are formulated in such a way that the interaction of the interlocutors when working in pairs is also communicative or conditionally communicative, for example:

- dialogical speech: Fill in the gaps with verbs in the past tense and ask questions to the interlocutor: What did he do during the holidays? / Form questions with phrases and interview your interlocutor.
- monologue speech: Read the phrases and tell me what is fashionable now and what is out of fashion? / Tell us about the climate in Russia and the weather in different seasons. / What pieces of furniture go well together? / Tell us about the education and professions of your parents or grandparents.

It should also be noted special attention in the multimedia class is given to the formation of speaking competencies, where this happens along with work on pronunciation skills and auditory skills. After completing the listening tasks, students act out the dialogues according to the sample or modify them using a different lexical and meaningful content. Students also transmit the content of the texts they listened to in monologue, orally and in writing, and create their own texts based on the material of the program. An important point is the socio-cultural component of teaching foreign languages, so all multimedia tasks are authentic. The "Practical German Course" is accompanied by a CD with a recording of the introductory phonetic course and the textbook dialogues, which makes it possible to work on pronunciation, while the "listening" component is absent in this course.

In the "Practical Course of the German Language" there are no tasks for the formation of writing skills. Even in Lesson VII, which discusses mail and communication, there are rules for writing a formal email, but there is no assignment to write an email. In the EMC "Im Klartext A2" a large number of sample emails are given, tasks to write emails or texts of other functional styles: advertising, biography, news, blog / forum post, etc.

Discussions

Traditional, classical textbooks of foreign languages have shown their effectiveness in teaching several generations of specialists and contain a large number of various exercises and tasks aimed at developing linguistic and communicative competence, especially in the field of oral speech. It seems possible to undertake a comprehensive analysis of domestic teaching aids and textbooks of the second half of the 20th century in order to create the most complete classification of exercises and tasks for the formation of individual skills, abilities and competencies in each type of speech activity and further use the most effective established teaching practices. New tasks facing teachers of foreign languages, in particular, the development of socio-cultural, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, discursive and strategic subcompetencies, require critical analysis, rethinking and expedient transfer of the achievements of foreign theorists and practitioners of teaching methods of foreign languages in the education system of the Russian Federation.

Conclusion

The analysis of the content and structure of the classical textbook and the education-methodical complex of a new type allows us to draw the following conclusions. Russian higher professional education is beginning to focus on modern trends in the compilation of textbooks and educational and methodological complexes in foreign languages, taking into account the requirements of the labor market and the multicultural environment. When developing new manuals, it is necessary to revise the content and structure, as well as revise the traditional lexical and grammar exercises and use them in combination with speech tasks, shifting the emphasis from the linguistic component to the communicative one, in particular, the system of exercises and tasks should implement the task of developing students' ability to intercultural interaction. All selected materials, both texts and textual content of lexical and grammar exercises, must be authentic and correspond to modern reality. Modern teaching materials should be accompanied by audio and video materials of the appropriate level. Such changes will create favorable conditions for the formation of communicative, socio-cultural and professional competencies of students, increase the interest and motivation of students to learn a foreign language, and, ultimately, achieve better results in the learning process.

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